

A highly selective and sensitive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(III) using 3-hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one

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3-Hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) forms a 1 : 1 (V : HTC) yellow complex with V^{III} species at 47–57° in 0.03–0.14 M CH_3COOH medium which is extracted into CCl_4 having a λ_{max} at 420 nm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and standard deviation are $7.45 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.0007 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$ and ± 0.0012 absorbance unit, respectively. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0–0.85 $\mu\text{g V}$ per ml. Presence of a large number of elements do not interfere. The method has good reproducibility and can be satisfactorily applied for the analysis of industrial samples.

Most of the work pertaining to spectrophotometric determination of vanadium has been carried out in its pentavalent state^{1–5}. The state-III of the metal ion though relatively much less known, is quite important analytically as it can be easily produced by simple reduction of vanadium(v) with sodium dithionite. It has been found that vanadium(III) forms an extractable coloured complex with 3-hydroxy-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) in acidic medium, which forms the basis of a sensitive spectrophotometric method of determination of vanadium in trace amounts offering the advantages of high selectivity and reproducibility in the analysis of many synthetic and technical samples.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(III) obtained by sodium dithionite reduction⁶ of vanadium(v), gave a yellow complex with HTC in weak acetic acid media which was quantitatively extracted into carbon tetrachloride with a single contact. Fading of the colour was observed in strong acids like HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and $HClO_4$. The carbon tetrachloride solution showed λ_{max} at 415–423 nm where the reagent blank showed negligible absorbance.

Vanadium(III) complex was extracted into a large number of water-immiscible organic solvents. The absorbance decreased in the order : carbon tetrachloride > dichloromethane > benzene > 1,2-dichloroethane > chloroform > toluene > isoamyl alcohol > isoamyl acetate = butanol > cyclohexane > isobutyl methyl ketone. A single extraction with equal volume (10 ml) of carbon tetrachloride gave quantitative extraction and maximum absorbance of the complex, the absorbance being stable for at least 20 min.

The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 125–

250 mg sodium dithionite, 0.03–0.14 M acetic acid medium, 0.6–1.3 ml of 0.05% (w/v) HTC solution (in ethanol) for $\leq 8.5 \mu\text{g V}^{III}$ per 10 ml aqueous solution maintained at 47–57° and equilibrating once with an equal volume of carbon tetrachloride for 12–300 s at room temperature (25°). Low value of absorbance (0.350) was observed if the heating was not done during complex formation. Beer's law was valid in the concentration range 0–0.85 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of vanadium. However, the optimum range of determination as evaluated from Ringbom plot was found to be 0.20–0.59 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $7.45 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0007 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively, at 420 nm. The reproducibility of the method was tested by performing ten sets of experiments keeping the same amount ($0.5 \mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$) of the metal ion each time. The standard deviation was ± 0.0012 absorbance unit. The stoichiometry of the complex as determined by Job's method of continuous variations was found to be 1 : 1 which was further supported by the mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the proposed method containing $5 \mu\text{g V}^{III}$, the ions/complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts in 10 ml aqueous phase (mg amounts in parentheses) such as chloride, bromide, iodide, sulfate, phosphate, thiourea (100 each); nitrate (90); thiocyanate (80); nitrite (50); bicarbonate (30); carbonate (30); ascorbic acid (20); acetate (10); tartrate (1); H_2O_2 (6%, w/v; 0.5 ml) did not influence the absorbance of the complex. However, fluoride, citrate, oxalate and disodium EDTA even in traces interfered seriously. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion which caused an error of ± 0.02 in the absorbance measurement, which corresponds to $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of vanadium. V^{III} ($5 \mu\text{g}$) could be determined without interference in presence of ≥ 500 -fold excess of

Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mg^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ba^{II} and Al^{III}; ≥100-fold excess of Be^{II}, U^{VI}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sr^{II} and Cr^{VI}; ≥10-fold excess of Ti^{IV}, Cu^{II}, Th^{IV}, Ir^{III}, Sn^{II}, W^{VI}, Se^{IV}, As^V and Ag^I; ≥3-fold excess of Ce^{IV}, Nb^V, Pt^{IV}, Re^{VII}, Sb^{III}, Cr^{III}, Au^{III} and Pd^{II}, and equivalent amounts of Os^{VIII}, Ru^{III} and Ta^V. Upto 0.1 mg of Fe^{III} and 0.01 mg of Zr^{IV} were masked with 20 and 10 mg, respectively, of ascorbic acid, when added prior to the addition of HTC.

Application : The applicability of the method was tested by analyzing several synthetic (some of them analogous to palau and permendur) and technical samples, namely, high speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust, with satisfactory results (Table 1).

The proposed method was found to be simple, highly reproducible, rapid and superior as it was more sensitive and selective than most of the existing methods of vanadium determination (Table 2).

Table 1. Determination of V in synthetic and real samples

Sl. no	Composition (mg)	V added μg	V found* μg
1.	Ni (0.06), Pt (0.02), Pd (0.02) ^a	5	4.84
2.	Fe (0.10), Co (0.1), Mn (0.001) ^{ab}	3	3.00
3.	Co (5), Ba (5), Ni (2)	6	5.99
4.	Mg (5), Be (1), Pb (0.1)	5	5.00
5.	Cu (0.1), Zn (1), Hg (0.1)	2	2.01
6.	Os (0.01), Au (0.01), Pt (0.01)	1	0.97
7.	Ru (0.01), Re (0.01), Se (0.01)	3	3.03
8.	Mo (0.01), Cr (0.01), Pd (0.01)	5	4.93
9.	Cr ^{III} (0.01), Zr (0.005), Ir (0.1) ^c	5	4.84
10.	Reverberatory flue dust (100) ^b	5	4.94
11.	High speed steel super rapid extra 500 (50)	1% ^d	0.988%

*Average of duplicate analyses. ^aCompositions analogous to palau, permendur, respectively. ^bIn presence of 20 mg ascorbic acid. ^cIn presence of 10 mg ascorbic acid. ^dCertified value.

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous condition	Solvent (λ _{max} , nm)	Sandell's sensitivity. μg cm ⁻² (Molar absorptivity, dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Interfering metal ions
1.	V ^V , 0.0–0.5 M CH ₃ COOH, 0.1% 2'-hydroxyacetophenone-benzoylhydrazone in acetone ^a	Chloroform (375)	0.0057 (8.93 × 10 ³)	
2.	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5, picolinealdehyde benzothiazolyhydrazone ^b	– (528)	0.0033 (1.54 × 10 ⁴)	Fe ^{II, III} , Co ^{II} , Pd ^{II}
3.	V ^V , pH 5.0–7.0, 5-(4-diethylamino-phenylazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline Triton-X-100 ^c	– (525)	0.0011 (4.74 × 10 ⁴)	Not known
4.	V ^V , 0.18–0.44 M CH ₃ COOH, 0.3% 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2'-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one in ethanol, heating at 33–35 ^{od}	Chloroform (432)	0.0012 (3.98 × 10 ⁴)	Mo ^{VI}
5.	V ^V , 0.04–0.06 M HCl, 0.2% 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-7-methyl-2-(2-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one in acetone, heating at 32 ± 1 ^{oe}	CCl ₄ (417–425)	0.0006 (8.26 × 10 ⁴)	Sn ^{II}
6.	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5 ^f	0.1% Oxine in chloroform (550)	0.016 (3.18 × 10 ³)	Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , U ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Bi ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III}
7.	V ^V , pH 5.5–8.5, 0.2% 5,7-diiodoxine in acetone, dithionite, heating at 60 ^{og}	Chloroform (415)	0.0067 (7.58 × 10 ³)	Fe ^{II, III}
8.	V ^V , pH 6–8, dithionite, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline ^h	Chloroform (420)	0.006 (7.27 × 10 ³)	Mo ^{VI}
9.	V ^V , 0.05 M H ₂ SO ₄ , Ferron ⁱ	1-Butanol (430)	0.011 (4.58 × 10 ³)	Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , Fe ^{II, III}
10.	V ^V , 0.06 M CH ₃ COOH, dithionite, 0.5% 3-hydroxyflavone, colour development time 10 min ^j	Dichloroethane (400)	0.0014 (3.56 × 10 ⁴)	Ti ^{IV} , Al ^{III}
11.	Present method	CCl ₄ (415–423)	0.0007 (7.45 × 10 ⁴)	36 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 3. ^dRef. 4. ^eRe. 5. ^fRef. 9. ^gRef. 10. ^hRef. 11. ⁱRef. 12. ^jRef. 13.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 140-02 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. Solutions of V^V and other ions were prepared as reported earlier⁷. 3-Hydroxy-2-(2-

thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one (HTC) (m.p. 200°) was synthesized⁸ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.05% (w/v) solution. A 2 M acetic acid solution was prepared. Carbon tetrachloride (Qualigens SQ) was used as such.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of vanadium(v) and other metal ions in suitable proportions. High speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust samples were brought into solution as reported¹ and vanadium determined in the aliquots by proposed method after adding ascorbic acid (20 mg) in each case.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing $\leq 8.5 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$ were added sodium dithionite (150 mg), 2 M CH_3COOH (0.4 ml), 0.05% HTC (1 ml) and the volume was made upto 10 ml with deionized water. The content was heated to 47–57°, then cooled to room temperature and equilibrated with CCl_4 (10 ml) for 30 s. The yellow organic phase was filtered to remove water droplets, if any and its absorbance was measured at 420 nm against the reagent blank.

For each of 0.1 mg Fe^{III} and 0.01 mg Zr^{IV} , when present, 20 and 10 mg, respectively, ascorbic acid, was added as the masking agent prior to the addition of HTC in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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